

Minutes of the 63rd Experimenters' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 20th June 2019

(This document was finalised on 31st January 2020)

Present:

(BB)	Dr Barbara Brooks ^{1,4,7}	
(CFL)	Dr Chris Lee	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ^{2,4,6}	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{4,5,6}	Secretary
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ^{4,8}	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ^{4,8}	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ^{4,8}	
(JP)	Dr Jeremy Price ³	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ⁵	

Affiliation:

¹ (AMF)	Atmospheric Measurement Facility
² (CFARR)	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research
³	Met Office
⁴ (NCAS)	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
⁵	NERC MST Radar Facility
⁶ (RAL)	STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
⁷	University of Leeds
⁸	University of Manchester

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
BST	British Summer Time
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Analysis
ESA	European Space Agency
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
GAP	Graham Parton (CEDA data scientist)
GMT	Greenwich Mean Time
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NFARR	NERC Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research
UKSBS	UK Shared Business Services
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
UTC	Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GV pointed out that the model described in section 6b of the minutes for the 62nd meeting was run by the University of Manchester Centre for Atmospheric, i.e. "ManU-CAS" - not "Manucast" as shown in the minutes.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

DISCONTINUED

This action has now been superseded by item 62.2.3.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

COMPLETED

A report on this action will be given in section 4b.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had now received the files from the Met Office, but that he had not yet made them publicly available.

ACTION ITEM 59.3.1 DAH to arrange for the clearance of willow saplings from the MST radar's antenna array as soon as possible.

COMPLETED

A report on the action above will be given in section 3d.

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the version 4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which version 3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had started to fill in the gap between June 2006, when version 3 files started to be made available routinely, and June 2011, from when version 4 files are already available continuously.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH to introduce a mechanism to allow users to access data files that have not yet passed quality control checks and been delivered to the CEDA archives.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had recently tried making files available to GV through his STFC-provided OneDrive account. Although this had ultimately been successful, it was problematic. It's not clear whether or not GV would have managed to download the files had he not also had a OneDrive account. BB recommended using the NCAS-provided Google drive. She also thought it might be possible to give people access to DAH's "quarantine" area, perhaps through the "ncas_obs" group workspace on the jasmin system. GV pointed out that he didn't have an account on jasmin. BB recommended that DAH should speak to James Groves.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.1 DAH to make the backlog of LD40 and WXT520 data available through CEDA in NCAS-approved files.

ONGOING

DAH now has much of the software needed for this action. However, he still needs to agree file details with BB.

ACTION ITEM 62.2.2 DAH to make available machine-readable files to show the number of MST radar transmitters in operation at any one time.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 62.2.3 DAH to come up with a plan for creating version 4 MST radar data for dates when no version 3 files are available.

ONGOING

Note that this supersedes item 47.2.1

ACTION ITEM 62.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a consistent archive structure for the different versions of MST Radar data products files.

ONGOING

GV pointed out that although it was clear that directories existed for versions 0 - 3 in the top level data directory, the existence of a version 4 directory was hidden within a subdirectory. DAH pointed out that the CEDA-provided usage statistics indicated that the uptake of version 4 data had been good.

ACTION ITEM 62.3.2 DAH and CJW to manage the installation of the new MST radar transmitters, which will require help from additional members of Chilbolton group staff, for the latter part of 2019.

ONGOING

GV warned that the NCAS finance office can be very slow to get things done and so DAH should get something initiated before the summer holiday period.

ACTION ITEM 62.4.1 DAH to provide BB with a list of all of the instruments operated by the MSTRF and of all of the data products available. DAH should provide as much detail as possible.

ONGOING

ACTION ITEM 62.4.2 DAH to send BB details of raw LD40 data products so that the most appropriate way of storing them in netCDF files can be agreed.

ONGOING

DAH pointed out that he had been able to supply HMAR and GV with sample LD40 backscatter files, but that he had not yet agreed an NCAS-compliant file implementation. BB clarified that if a particular variable is defined within an NCAS standard, it does not have to be used if there are no data to populate it with. However, it may not be used to store non-standard data, for which a new variable name must be used.

ACTION ITEM 62.7.1 DAH to contact EUCOS, before the end of March 2019, to arrange for near-real-time MST radar wind-profile to continue to be delivered to the E-PROFILE programme.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that the data continue to be sent to EUCOS. There was a general discussion about the limitations of the Mode S system that the Met Office are now relying on for their upper air wind measurements - the data are taken from the sensors on commercial aircraft. The location of Mode S data are biased towards the major airports, have relatively poor coverage at night, and are unavailable when strong low-level winds prevent aircraft landing and taking off.

GV reported that there was NCAS capital money to purchase a Lufft ceilometer for the Capel Dewi site. It is expected to be delivered towards the end of 2019. HMAR already has experience of using this model and so has worked out how to overcome some of its quirks. BB pointed out that if it is contributing the NCAS long term measurement programme, the data files must be NCAS-compliant. BB also clarified that NCAS-compliant files must use the "netCDF 4 classic" format (DAH's files currently used the "netCDF 3 classic" format).

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

Graham Parton (GAP) was unable to attend the meeting and so there was no official report from the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA). DAH reported that he (DAH) had experienced frequent and diverse problems with the jasmin computing facility over the past 6 months. These had led to delays in data files being made available. Of particular note was the fact that the new web server was not showing the availability of the most recent plots. Although it was possible to find these files, initially by following a link to "*view most recent listings*", the process was convoluted and had to be repeated for each individual file. Consequently DAH had written a script to copy the latest plots to his desktop, from where he could view them more conveniently (viewing the plots is the final stage of his quality control procedure before releasing the corresponding data files to the archives).

3b) Electricity - DAH

The electricity accounts for a number of NERC facilities are still connected, despite the fact that responsibility for paying the bills was devolved to the individual facilities several years ago. This meant that the person responsible for the Centre for Ecology and Hydrology's (CEH's) Auchencorth site was able to accidentally pay the Capel Dewi bill for April 2019. Ironically, DAH would probably have been able to pay Auchencorth's bill in return had he not just succeeded (after 4 years of trying) in getting British Gas (the supplier) to remove his "*super user*" status. This had allowed him to view the details of all of the other former NERC accounts. For reasons of data protection, British Gas will no longer take credit card payments over the phone. Moreover, DAH cannot find a way of transferring money between STFC and NERC, despite the fact they both now sit under the umbrella of the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). DAH is still in the process of trying to resolve the issue.

The Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) units only had to switch to battery power on 5 brief (i.e. ~ 1 s) occasions during the last 6 months. These all occurred during April 2019. DAH inspected the units when he visited Capel Dewi in April 2019. The unit labelled TX1, which powers transmitter TXA, has not sent any notification e-mails since 2017. DAH thinks that this is related to the fact that the unit was replaced and so has a different model of network card compared to the other units. However, it's not clear why this is preventing it from sending any notifications. This unit developed a battery fault on 12th June 2019, since when the transmitters TXA and TXC have both been powered by the unit for TXC. The batteries for all units were last changed in late 2015 or early 2016. They are reaching the end of their expected life spans.

LD drew attention to the fact that the ATRAD company had supplied only a single, low-capacity UPS

unit with the new equipment that is due to be installed. He did not think it would provide much uptime in the case of a loss of mains electricity. BB reported that she had a 1500 kVA unit in Leeds, which could be borrowed for temporary use.

ACTION ITEM 63.3.1 DAH to contact ATRAD in order to clarify the Uninterruptible Power Supply requirements for the new radar equipment.

NEW

The septic tank was emptied at the end of April 2019.

3c) Telecommunications

DAH reported that he had transferred billing for the “alarm line” from BT to KCOM (formerly known as Eclipse), who were already responsible for the “phone” and “fax” lines. The move was triggered by BT cutting off the line in late March 2019 owing to non-payment of the January 2019 bill. DAH didn't know about this until early April when he had to phone BT to find out why he couldn't log on to their website in order to pay the subsequent bill. Despite the fact that DAH's account was “paperless”, BT sent out the final demand for the the January 2019 bill by post. This failed to reach him in time since anything that looks like a utility bill tends to get diverted from the STFC postal system to UK Shared Business Services (UKSBS). This was not the first time that DAH had had matters arising from a Capel Dewi utility bill having been appropriated by UKSBS.

Since DAH was already of the opinion that BT provided poor customer service and poor value for money, he was quite pleased to have an excuse to change provider. KCOM's package includes a 50 Gbyte broadband download limit for less than BT charged for just line rental. Even if this additional broadband connection is not used on a routine basis, DAH thought it would be useful to have a spare line that could be used either for the MSTRF or Manchester networks if a fault develops on the primary line. At the time of the meeting, the line was still not active owing to the fact that the BT connection was cut off rather than being transferred.

3d) Miscellaneous

The clearance of the willow saplings from the antenna array of the MST Radar finally took place during the first week of June 2019. DAH conceded that being obliged to go through one of STFC's “Facilities Management” contract holders had eventually proved to be useful. Although it had taken over 2 years to get the contract set up, work began within two weeks of DAH being able to access the NERC funds being held by NCAS (which itself took 3 months to set up). The people who actually carried out the work (they were subcontractors to a subcontractor to STFC's primary contractor) were local to the Aberystwyth area. They preferred to start work as early as possible and so DAH arrived on site before 8 am each day to let them in. DAH was impressed by how hard they had worked, especially given that the work was very repetitive and that the weather had been bad for much of the week. It turns out that they had cut through one of the antenna feeds (unit 61). However, DAH was able to identify this from the monitoring software for the beam steering units and LD was subsequently able to repair the feed. They didn't quite finish the job by the end of week and had to come back for one day on the following week.

There was a general discussion as to what could be done to prevent the willows becoming a problem again in the future. LD pointed out that the drainage system for the antenna field had become clogged up and that the collected water was contributing to the problem of willow growth. CFL suggested that if the field was to be dug up, it would be useful to unearth the radar cables and to put them in above-ground conduits at the same time. However, he noted that if soil had gotten in to the existing subterranean conduits, they would be almost impossible to dig up. He suggested that the best time for spraying vegetation was in the autumn.

DAH pointed out that now the willows had been cleared, it was possible to see what other work needed

to be carried out within the antenna array. The “chicken shacks” that house the primary power splitters are in a poor condition and need to be replaced. Some of the antenna support structures are also corroded in parts. It would also be good to cut back the trees that are starting to overhang the lidar units and the main electricity supply for the site. DAH suggested that BB and CJW should visit the Capel Dewi site so that they had a better idea of its capabilities.

The fire extinguishers at the site were inspected during the first week of February 2019.

The renewal of LD's contract for part-time technical support in April 2019 was delayed by 2 weeks. This was the result of DAH not having clear guidelines about what was required. LD stayed away from the site until the new contract had been finalised.

The MSTRF already merged with the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR) in April 2018 to form the NERC Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (NFARR). NFARR will itself merge with the Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) to form the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF) in April 2020. Despite all of these changes, users should not notice any changes to their ability to access the MSTRF and the long-running series of Experimenters' meetings will continue.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

DAH began by showing how he updated the style of the wind rose plots for Frongoch (i.e. Campbell Scientific) and Capel Dewi (i.e. Vaisala WXT510) surface wind measurements based on feedback provided by JP at the previous meeting. These show very clearly how the Capel Dewi wind direction is tightly constrained by the valley's ENE-WSW alignment. He showed the time-series data for 22nd January 2008, when the Frongoch measurements showed winds from the south, i.e. approximately perpendicular to the alignment of the Capel Dewi valley. The Capel Dewi measurements show periods when the wind direction is not constrained and changes rapidly. These are accompanied by wind speeds that are much faster than seen at Frongoch.

GV commented that it was sometimes possible to see the change in wind direction with from valley-aligned to background flow when radiosonde balloons were launched from the site. He suggested looking for such a signature in BLWP data.

DAH drew attention to the fact that the definitions of the 60 s interval data produced by the Campbell Scientific and Vaisala WXT510 instruments are different. This is because the Campbell Scientific sensors are sampled continuously at 1 s intervals whereas the Vaisala WXT510 sensors are sampled for only 3 s out of every 60, albeit at 0.25 s intervals. This means that the minimum and maximum gust speeds are much more closely correlated with the mean speed in the case of the Vaisala WXT510 than in the case of the Campbell Scientific sensors. DAH showed that the ratios of minimum/maximum gust speeds to mean wind speed were (on average, based on 8 years of data) 0.87/1.13 for the Vaisala WXT510 data and 0.63/1.40 for the Campbell Scientific. The values produced by the Campbell Scientific strategy are clearly more appropriate.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

DAH reported that there had been no serious issues with these sensors over the past six months. Nevertheless, he drew attention to a couple of strange measurements. The tipping bucket indicated an accumulation of 0.2 mm of rain (i.e. one tip) for the 10 minute period starting at 10:20 UTC on 30th January 2019 whilst the Vaisala WXT520 recorded 1.06 mm. The air temperature was 3°C at the time, so DAH wondered whether the tipping bucket had failed to quantify the amount of mixed phase precipitation. In a second case on the following day, the tipping bucket indicated an accumulation of 0.2 mm of rain for each of the 10 minute periods starting at 12:10, 15:50, and 18:00 UTC. The Vaisala WXT520 detected

no rain during these periods and the backscatter power from the Vaisala LD40 ceilometer only indicated rain during the 3rd of the periods.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

The Campbell Scientific CR10 data logger, which had been in operation since 1995, was replaced by a Campbell Scientific CR1000X logger on 4th June 2019. DAH had been operating the new logger, without sensors attached, in his office for most of April 2019 so that he could check whether data downloads via a 3G modem were working (the old logger relied on a dial-up modem via a land line). He then installed the logger at Frongoch, again without sensors attached, on 24th April 2019 so that he could be sure that 3G reception was not a problem. He and LD finally switched over the sensors from the old to the new logger on 4th June 2019. Despite the fact that the Campbell Scientific logger software provides a number of methods of calculating 60 s interval gust and mean wind speeds, it does not offer the method used by the old logger. Consequently DAH decided to simply save all of the raw 1 s interval samples of wind speed and direction and then to recreate the processing in Python software.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

There have been no issues with this instrument over the past 6 months.

DAH addressed the need to include missing datum values in the netCDF files to indicate periods when the instrument was not collecting data. He showed an example from 31st March 2008, when no data were collected for over 6 hours, using the freely-available [panoply data viewing software](#). If missing datum values are included, the software shows a gap, but otherwise joins the data points immediately preceding and following the gap with a straight line. The situation is slightly different for precipitation data since the WXT instruments only produce precipitation messages during a precipitation event. DAH demonstrated that this can lead the panoply software to show “ramps” between the zero rain rate at the end of one precipitation event and the non-zero value at the start of the next event.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

DAH reported that had begun to discuss an NCAS-compliant way of storing the data from the LD40 with BB. The instrument is not designed for research purposes and so the backscattered power is only available in the form of a binned range-squared-corrected value. During April 2019 he produced some non-NCAS-compliant files for GV and is able to do so for anyone else on request.

4e) Sky Cameras

There is nothing to report on this instrument for the past 6 months.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH found that the power adapter had failed when he first tried to start the NLC camera on 29th May 2019. A new adapter was installed on 7th June and the first NLC was seen during the dawn of 9th June.

4g) MST Radar

DAH noticed that the wrong values (0.0 - 1.0 instead of 0.0 - 20.0) were being shown for the “horizontal wind speed complementary beam variability” factor on the “diagnostic” plots. He corrected this on 18th February 2019. However, he didn't think that there was much point in recreating the earlier plots since he is probably the only person who looks at these plots.

The radar was powered down 11:22 - 12:03 UTC on 15th February 2019. This was to allow LD to carry out tests on the power splitter feeding quad 90, which had been producing unusual readings.

The radar transmitters for antenna sectors A and E were taken off-line between approximately 10:50 and 11:50 UTC and on 18th March 2019. This was to allow students from Aberystwyth University to carry out their surveying practical on the antenna array.

DAH has labelled a number of data files as “suspect” since they contain unrealistic-looking wind speeds within small time-altitude regions: 15:30 - 16:00 UTC around 17.5 km on 9th March 2019; 13:10 - 13:50 UTC around 18.0 km, 17:45 - 18:15 UTC around 19.0 km, and 23:30 - 23:59 UTC around 18.0 km on 10th March; 02:40 - 03:20 around 16.5 km UTC on 11th March; 21:30 - 23:30 UTC above 16.0 km on 12th March; 02:30 - 03:10 UTC around 16 km on 13th March. These outliers were all associated with mountain wave activity.

DAH has finally understood what causes a timing error when civilian time changes from Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) to British Summer Time (BST) at the end of March - 31st March in 2019. It is a result of the version of the Python programming language that he used to write the data processing software not yet offering the *datetime.strptime* method. Instead, in order to derive datetime information from a string, he had to make use of the *time.strptime* and *time.mktime* methods followed by the *datedatetime.datetime.fromtimestamp* method. This has the unexpected effect of interpreting times between 01:00 and 02:00 UTC on the morning of the GMT to BST change as occurring between 02:00 and 03:00 UTC. The strings were interpreted appropriately at all other times, including around the period when BST reverts back to GMT in late October.

The radar receiver noise floor was raised between the late evening of 12th June 2019 and the early afternoon of the following day. This is particularly obvious in the plot of mesospheric data, but reductions in useful altitude coverage are apparent in the standard st-mode plots as well.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN gave a report on the Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler (BLWP). She has been looking at the log files, which record all of the issues affecting the BLWP on a year-by-year basis. Velocity aliasing and problems with PCA remain the most common issues. The BLWP suffered from one problem after another during the early part of 2019. Not all of the suggestions given by the manufacturer were effective. New PCA software was released on 22nd February 2019, although after ongoing problems the PCA computer was replaced in April 2019. However, there were problems almost immediately. EGN had to remove the digital signal processing board on multiple occasions. She finally got the system working after a piece of the board fell out and she put it back.

EGN commented on the fact that the Met Office's BLWP at Chilbolton is looking in a sorry state. CJW explained that STFC's legal team are still trying to find a relevant person at the Met Office so that the BLWP can officially be donated to NCAS. A member of Met Office staff is due to visit Chilbolton shortly and he is aware of the proposed hand-over of the BLWP. A licence will be required for the BLWP if it is put back into operation.

GV gave a short report on the lidars. There have been a variety of problems with the Elight lidar over the past 6 months. Dave Wareing has fixed most things, including the temperature control. He has 3D printed replacement valves for the pump. The crystal for producing the 3rd harmonic is damaged and overheats. GV would like to get it re-polished. The Raman channel is now working and good data have been collected for aerosol profiling. The big lidar is in working condition but the weather has not been suitable for making observations. There has been lots of forest fire smoke this year. The SAOZ instrument is still working as far as GV knows. The data are sent to NDAC and are being used.

BB noted that the NCAS calendars currently show the the lidar and BLWP as being operational. The calendars should be updated when the instruments are not operational.

GV followed up with a short presentation about the new the Atmospheric Measurement and Observation Facility (AMOF). The merger of the existing NFARR and AMF is being undertaken since this is what

NERC wants. Nevertheless, it will have the advantages of creating a larger pool of expertise and staff availability. The main aims of AMOF include creating data and metadata to high international standards; implementing standard operating principles; providing appropriate software tools to access and utilise the data. AMOF will combine in situ and remote sensing instruments and will be able to support studies of clouds and precipitation, winds, boundary-layer and turbulence, and composition. The management structure has not yet been finalised, although there will be two divisions with GV having an oversight of both. The MSTRF will become known as an Observatory rather than as a facility. Although only a quarter of the MSTRF is funded as a facility (the rest being funded through the long term measurement programme), it makes logistical sense to consider it as being a part of AMOF.

The NCAS Data Project has proved to require a lot more work than was originally anticipated. BB has had to spend large amounts of time working on the fine details. The main reason for adopting well-defined data and metadata standards is to make it easier to create software tools that can handle any NCAS data file. The scanning radars will have their own standard, which will be based on the existing CfRadial standard. All data processing is expected to take place on the jasmin platform.

AMOF will prioritise applications in the following order: NERC Grants, non-NERC research council funded projects, NERC National Capability, Direct Access, EU grants and public not-for-profit projects, and commercial organisations. Grant funded projects will adopt the grades awarded by the relevant council's peer review panel. Direct Access projects will have to be graded by members of AMOF's steering committee.

The existing MSTRF and CFARR users' meetings will be regarded as AMOF working groups since they encourage the sharing of best practices, discuss relevant issues, influence the development of the facilities, and discuss science. More working groups will follow.

AMF has so far deliberately avoided including the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) as part of its official activities. This is partly since it would not be in a position to provide members of staff who are capable of flying the UAVs. NCAS is waiting for a clear indication from the community as to how this area should be developed. There will be a town meeting to discuss the subject on 1st August 2019. JP pointed out that it was important to develop standards for the most appropriate ways to make UAV-based measurements.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Boundary-Layer Wind-profiler Observations at Capel Dewi - CFL and EGN

A study conducted 2 years ago showed that the long term average of vertical velocities observed by the BLWP when it was operated at Capel Dewi showed a noticeable positive (i.e. upward) bias. However, the corresponding average for the MST radar did not. In order to investigate this further, one year's worth of observations were collected between September 2017 and September 2018. Only "high-mode" data were used from the BLWP, covering the altitude range 250 - 5800 m. The useful altitude coverage was slightly reduced compared to that seen during the previous study. Nevertheless, data were still available for 75% of the time at altitudes below 3 km.

Only data from precipitation-free conditions were considered. Data were binned according to the horizontal wind speed observed at an altitude of 2 km. Despite using a longer dataset than in the previous study, CFL found the same positive bias. This is unexpected since any contamination from precipitation would be expected to give rise to a negative bias. When the data are analysed as a function of (2 km) wind direction, there is a clear sinusoidal variation with a peak-to-trough amplitude of 0.2 m s^{-1} . This suggests that the pointing direction of the vertical beam is off from the vertical by approximately 0.5° - 0.75° . GV thanked JP for having suggested this line of enquiry. EGN pointed out that it was not possible to level the vertical beam antenna panel with an accuracy of better than 0.5° . CFL concluded

that this was the fundamental limitation of the instrument. Errors in the estimate of the vertical velocity propagate through to errors in the estimate of the horizontal wind speed. CFL had only just managed to create a plot looking at off-vertical beam data on the day before this presentation. It shows a similar sort of pattern.

CFL clarified that the azimuthal alignment of the BLWP was carried out using a magnetic compass. HMAR pointed out that the direction of magnetic north drifts slowly over time. EGN commented that using a magnetic compass near the metal structure of the BLWP was also problematic. GV pointed out that the winds had been predominantly westerly during the previous observation period and so it had been important to capture winds from other directions. He was pleased that a suitable method of analysis was now available to reveal this issue. He stressed that an important result was that vertical velocities could only be relied upon to within 0.1 m s^{-1} . DAH suggested that it might be possible to verify the beam pointing direction using the radio star method of [Campistron et al., 2001](#).

6b) ESAs ADM Aeolus wind-measuring satellite mission - DAH DAH gave a short presentation on the [European Space Agency's \(ESA's\) ADM Aeolus wind-profiling satellite mission](#). He had attended a Cal/Val workshop back in March 2019. The satellite relies on an ultra-violet laser, which had initially had a detrimental effect on the optics when it was operated in a vacuum. This had delayed the start of the mission (August 2018) until a solution was found for the problem. The receiver has both a Rayleigh scatter and a Mie scatter channel, the latter also allowing the detection of clouds. Signals can only be sampled for a fixed number of range bins and so the altitude resolution is somewhat limited. The transmitter has only a single pointing direction. Although this allows only a single component of the horizontal wind to be derived (the large zenith angle of 35° means that the vertical component can effectively be ignored), since this approximates to the zonal direction it is nevertheless useful for data assimilation purposes. The European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) in particular is keen to make operational use of the data since the satellite provides global coverage.

Although there have been some technical issues with the new instrument, ESA is broadly very pleased with the results. A number of organisations are helping with the validation work using, amongst other things, radiosonde, wind-profiler, aircraft, and model data. It turns out that one of the satellite profiles is quite close to Aberystwyth and so the MST radar could also contribute to this work. GV and CJW were both keen that DAH took part.

7. Any Other Business

JP pointed out that the MST radar had now been collecting data for almost 30 years. He wondered whether any climatologists had made use of the data. GV pointed out that it would be helpful, in this regard, to have version 4 processed data available for the whole observation archive.

The date for the next meeting was provisionally set as 23rd January 2020.